

Preliminary Note on the Action of *cyclo*-Hexene Oxide on Alkali and Ammonium Halides.

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In the course of a fermentative experiment, it was found necessary to treat an aqueous suspension of *cyclo*-hexene oxide with a saturated solution of ammonium chloride. The aqueous layer was noticed to have acquired slight alkalinity to litmus and in the course of two days the layer of *cyclo*-hexene oxide settled to the bottom. By this time the alkalinity had developed to such an extent that the ammonium chloride solution could be titrated with N/10 or N/100 sulphuric acid with methyl orange as indicator. The oxide (0.93 g.) and ammonium chloride (53.5 g.) made up to 220 c.c. by water and a few c. c. of alcohol, gave a closely agreeing constant for a pseudo-monomolecular reaction, the mean value of which was 0.116 at 34°. The proportions were 1 mol. of *cyclo*-hexene oxide to 100 mols. of ammonium chloride. The percentage of conversion of *cyclo*-hexene oxide into chlorhydrin was found at equilibrium to be about 80.

It was thought that probably the slight basicity of *cyclo*-hexene oxide was responsible for the alkalinity developed in ammonium chloride solution, but on treating a strong neutral solution of KCl, KBr or KI with a few drops of *cyclo*-hexene oxide as above, the alkalinity developed readily in a few minutes in the order, KI, KBr, KCl. The development of free KOH in potassium halide solutions can be demonstrated by adding a drop or two of phenolphthalein to the reaction mixture: a pink colour develops which can be discharged with carbonic acid. After a short time the colour reappears showing the further progress of the reaction as explained below.

This explanation, however, is tentative.

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